

Heterotopic pancreas in Gall Bladder with Associated Cholesterolosis, a Rare Entity

Gupta Latika*¹, Ahmed Baba Arshad²

1. Gupta Latika, (latika_gupta@yahoo.com), Consultant Histopathologist, Metropolis Healthcare Lab, New Delhi.

2. Ahmed Baba Arshad, (drarshadbaba@gmail.com), Consultant Surgeon, MBBS, MS, FACRSI, FIAGES, FMAS, District Hospital Kulgam, J&K

***Correspondence to:** Dr. Latika Gupta, MD Pathology, Consultant Histopathologist, Metropolis Healthcare Lab, New Delhi.

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Received: 25 January 2024

Published: 06 February 2024

Introduction

Heterotopic pancreas (HP) is a rare congenital anomaly, usually discovered incidentally in adulthood, defined as presence of ectopic or aberrant pancreatic tissue outside its normal location with absent vascular and anatomical connection to the main pancreatic tissue.¹ HP can be seen anywhere in the gastrointestinal tract, commonly found in stomach, duodenum, colon, esophagus and rarely in gall bladder, Meckel's diverticulum and even in choledochal cyst.² Here in, we report a case of HP in gall bladder of a 38 year female. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first case of HP in gall bladder with associated marked cholesterosis.

A 38 year old female presented with vomiting and pain abdomen in right upper quadrant. Routine investigations were normal. Ultrasonography showed well distended gall bladder of normal wall thickness with multiple tiny polyps, largest measuring 2.8mms [Fig 1a]. Laproscopic cholecystectomy was performed and Calot's triangle was found to be normal and free of any adhesions. On gross examination, gall bladder measured 8x3x1 cms. Neck showed nodular thickened area measuring 5mms and mucosa showed yellow streaks [Fig 1b].

Fig 1: (a) USG abdomen showing distended gall bladder and small multiple polyps largest measuring 2.8mms. (b) Gall bladder specimen showing yellow streaks in mucosa. Neck area is thickened focally.

Microscopic examination showed well circumscribed rest of ectopic pancreatic tissue in the serosal aspect of neck of gall bladder. The pancreatic rest comprised of lobules of acini and ducts. However, no islets were

identified [Fig 2a-c]. The rest of the gall bladder mucosa showed numerous collections of foamy histiocytes in lamina [Fig 2d]. The final diagnosis was established as chronic cholecystitis with cholesterolosis with pancreatic heterotopia.

Fig 2: Microphotographs showing (a), (b) and (c) respectively showing lobules of benign pancreatic acini and interspersed ducts in the serosal aspect of neck of gall bladder [H&E, 40X, 100X and 400X]. (d) Gall bladder mucosa showing abundant foamy histiocytes in lamina i.e. cholesterolosis [H&E, 200X].

Post operative course was uneventful and patient was discharged after 5 days.

HP in gall bladder is rare with incidence of 0.6-13.7%³. Female preponderance is noted with neck being the most common site⁴ as seen in the present case. According to the classification modified by Fuentes, four types of HP can be seen¹

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- (i) Type I: Resembles the normal pancreatic tissue with the presence of ducts, acini, and endocrine islets
 - (ii) Type II: Canalicular variant with pancreatic ducts
 - (iii) Type III or exocrine pancreas only
 - (iv) Type IV or endocrine pancreas only

Islets are seen only in 50% of the cases.³ The present case belongs to type III and islets were not seen.

The present case holds importance because chronic cholecystitis with marked cholesterolosis with PH has not been described before.

PH is usually underdiagnosed because radiological tools like CT scan or ultrasonography cannot differentiate between ectopic pancreatic tissue and other lesions like adenomas or polyp or neoplastic conditions.⁵ So was in the present case where ultrasound showed tiny polyps in gall bladder however neck region appeared unremarkable.

Incidentally detected heterotopic pancreas has potential to develop inflammatory or metaplastic or neoplastic changes.² Therefore, complete excision is adequate and preferred treatment of choice.¹

Heterotopic pancreas in gall bladder is a rare entity and histopathology examination is needed for definitive diagnosis. Awareness between pathologists and surgeons of this underreported entity may further facilitate the clinical significance of this entity.

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